

The Alan Turing Institute

Data Study Group Final Report: Global Witness

Identifying Unregulated Mining Sites
using Historical Satellite Data

**20 February -
3 March 2023**

Contents

1	Executive summary	2
1.1	Challenge overview	2
1.2	Main objectives	3
1.3	Data overview	3
1.4	Approach	4
1.5	Main conclusions	5
1.6	Limitations	5
2	Data	7
2.1	Labelled Pool Coordinates	7
2.2	Satellite Imagery	8
2.3	Data quality issues	11
3	Mine Detection	14
3.1	Spectral Indices	15
3.2	Pixel-based Classification with Random Forests	23
3.3	Deep learning for mine detection	28
4	Pool Detection	37
4.1	Template Matching	37
4.2	Deep learning for pool detection	46
5	Discussion and Future work	53
5.1	Discussion	53
5.2	Future Work	54
6	Team members	57

1 Executive summary

1.1 Challenge overview

Rare earth metals are a critical component in the manufacturing process of many electric vehicles, wind turbines, and consumer electronics such as mobile phones [1]. Demand for rare earth metals has increased rapidly in the past twenty years, and is expected to increase five-fold by 2040 [2].

China has historically dominated the global supply of rare earth elements, and is the largest producer of the manufactured products that require them. [1] However, many of China's domestic mines have been shut down due to concerns over pollution, which raises the question: Where does China obtain its supply of rare earth elements?

Reported quantities of Chinese imports of rare earth minerals from Myanmar have increased substantially in recent years; In 2014, Myanmar exported just \$1.5m of rare earths to China [1]. By 2021, this sum had reached \$740m [1]. However, a six month investigation by Global Witness [1] found a significant amount of illicit production and trade of these minerals in rebel-held areas along Myanmar's north-eastern border with China:

Figure 1: Comparison of satellite imagery in Pang War, Myanmar

Figure 1 shows the proliferation of illicit artisanal mines in the mountains north of the Pang War, a town on the border between Myanmar and China. This type of mining has devastating environmental consequences. Processing a single ton of rare earth elements can produce 2,000 tons of toxic waste [3]. Runoff from these pools leech directly into the N'Mai Kha river, which runs the length of Myanmar and whose basin is home to 2/3 of the country's population. The consequences of unregulated rare earth mining on human health and the environment are considerable.

1.2 Main objectives

Understanding the spatial distribution of these mines is a prerequisite for ultimately conducting cleanup efforts and gauging which populations might be affected by pollution. As such, the main objectives of this project are as follows:

1. Automate the identification of illicit rare earth mines in Myanmar using satellite imagery.
2. Train a model to identify individual pools within each mine.

The first objective is important for the purposes of monitoring the spread of these mines, which continue to propagate across Northern Myanmar. The second objective can help yield mine-level insights including estimating the potential productive capacity of each mine and its level of activity.

1.3 Data overview

There were two main categories of data used in this analysis. The first was a tabular dataset containing the known locations of mines, and the second was a range of different types of satellite imagery with varying spatial and spectral resolution. The satellite imagery ranged from high-resolution (but expensive and closed-source) SkySat imagery, to low-resolution (but free and open-access) Sentinel-2 imagery available on the European Space Agency's website [4]. Further details regarding the data used herein are summarised in Table 1.

Data	Description
Location of mining pools	CSV file containing the latitude and longitude coordinates of 2792 pools, in addition to the overall shape of the pool: either square or circular.
SkySat	High spatial resolution satellite images containing four bands of spectral data: red, green, blue and near-infrared. Each pixel represents $\approx 50\text{cm}$.
Sentinel-2	Public access satellite images, much lower spatial resolution than SkySat data, but much higher spectral resolution, containing 12 bands of spectral data. Spatial resolution is 10m for: B2, B3, B4, B8, 20m for: B5, B6, B7, B8a, B11, and B12 and 60m for B1, B9, and B10 [5].

Table 1: Overview of data by source.

1.4 Approach

The rest of this study proceeds as follows. Section 2.3.2 describes the datasets used for analysis and issues relating to data quality. Then, in accordance with the two objectives set forth, the analysis in this project is divided into two main sections.

Section 3 tackles the objective of mine detection in three ways:

- Section 3.1 explores Sentinel-2 Masking.
- Section 3.2 conducts segmentation using a Random Forest Algorithm.
- Section 3.3 conducts binary mine classification using a Convolution Neural Network (ResNet18).

Section 4 approaches the objective of pool detection two main approaches:

- Section 4.1 uses one-shot template matching to rapidly identify pools across a large area.

- Section 4.2 conducts object detection using a Faster-RCNN model for pool identification.

Finally, Section 5 conducts a discussion of the results and proposes avenues for further research.

1.5 Main conclusions

Following investigation of the above approaches, it was found that Sentinel-2 Masking provides relatively accurate areas of interest for possible mine locations. Random forests perform well for the segmentation of Sentinel-2 imagery, allowing the effective identification of mining sites. Using entirely open-access, medium resolution satellite imagery, F1 accuracy for the objective of mine identification was 0.82. The use of high resolution imagery and a ResNet 18 model yielded a maximal F1 accuracy of 0.977 for the task of classifying whether a given cropped image (within the overall area provided by the satellite imagery) contains a mine or not.

With respect to pool identification, template matching was found to be a simple and computationally efficient way of rapidly identifying pools across a large area, though these benefits come at the cost of accuracy. Object-detection using Faster-RCNN was much more accurate, and performed so well at detecting individual pools of different shapes that a number of unlabelled pools were discovered by filtering false positives with high confidence scores (see Figure 29).

1.6 Limitations

One of the major limitations of this investigation is the difficulty in assessing true F1 score for the pool-level detection task, further detailed in Section 2.3. This is due to problems with the labelled data, including a proportion of the pool coordinates being off-centre and the presence of unlabelled pools. As such, recall is used throughout, which gives an effective measure of how many of the labelled mines are accurately detected/classified by the different approaches, but does not give any indication as to the number of false positives by the models. A more

in-depth discussion of the limitations for each specific approach is given at the end of each respective section.

2 Data

This section provides an overview of the three main datasets used in the subsequent analysis:

1. A csv file of labelled precipitation pool coordinates
2. High resolution SkySat satellite imagery
3. Medium resolution Sentinel-2 satellite imagery

After introducing the datasets, three main challenges regarding data quality are explored. The first challenge involved uneven boundaries in the SkySat imagery which generated wholly or partially black images when cropped into smaller image tiles. A further challenge revolved around the incompleteness of labelled pools, which inflated the number of “false positives” as these were in fact precipitation pools, but were not identified in the labelling process. Finally, a systematic issue involving the shifting of some pool coordinates by several meters off-centre complicated the task of object detection, as the bounding boxes were consequently off-centre hampering the calculation of Intersection over Union and derivative accuracy statistics (e.g. mAP50) which are conventional in object detection tasks.

2.1 Labelled Pool Coordinates

The coordinates of 2,792 precipitation pools were collected manually by Global Witness, and form the basis for the training and evaluation of the mine and pool identification tasks.

The inset satellite in Figure 2 shows a close-up of one such mine; bright blue precipitation pools, used to precipitate out minerals from a slurry of ammonium sulphate and mud, are a characteristic feature of such mines.

Rare earth elements are seldom found in economically viable minable quantities in the Earth’s crust. Traditionally, the solvent-exchange method, where rock is broken into smaller pieces before being ground into a fine dust, is used to extract pure rare earth elements. Subsequent refinement by chemical techniques is used to separate the elements and remove

Figure 2: 2,792 precipitation pools labelled by Global Witness

unwanted materials (largely iron oxide and carbonate minerals), but this is time-consuming, expensive, and dangerous, sometimes requiring thousands of steps. Each rare earth element requires different chemical techniques for refining, and as such there is a very large amount of waste generated from their by-products. Once separated, an ore of rare earth elements and radioactive material remains, which is further separated using chemical leaching [6].

2.2 Satellite Imagery

Two main sources of satellite imagery were used in this analysis: SkySat and Sentinel-2.

2.2.1 SkySat

Planet's SkySat constellation provides optical satellite imagery at 50 centimetre per pixel resolution, and is capable of imaging the same point on earth 5-7 times per day [7]. Global Witness tasked the SkySat constellation to image the border region of Kachin, Myanmar, in March 2022. The collection is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Example skysat tiles plotted in RGB (Red, green, blue).

The high resolution of SkySat imagery enables the use of standard computer vision workflows such as template matching or object detection for the identification of individual pools.

2.2.2 Sentinel-2

The main disadvantage of SkySat and other high resolution imagery is that it is generally closed-source. This precludes multitemporal analysis, including the acquisition of more recent imagery over the area of interest, or in new areas.

In order to assess the viability of mine identification using open-access data, imagery from the European Space Agency's Sentinel-2 satellite will also be used. Despite its relatively low spatial resolution, multispectral satellite imagery from Sentinel-2 allows for the differentiation of materials such as water and vegetation on the basis of their spectral reflectance characteristics. The calculation of spectral indices—such as the Normalized Difference Water Index (NDWI)—highlights the pools used for the extraction of minerals in artisanal mines in Myanmar, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Sentinel-2 derived Normalized Difference Water Index over time

The inset line plot shows the NDWI value measured at the location of the yellow marker over time; although there is some noise, the measured point

achieves sustained positive NDWI values after August 2022. While the spatial resolution of 10 meters per pixel is too coarse to identify individual pools, the agglomerations of pools side by side generate high pixel values for certain spectral indices and allow for the identification of mines.

2.3 Data quality issues

2.3.1 Incompleteness of the Labelled Pools

In the initial phase of our investigation, the Skysat satellite data with coordinates marking the location of the pools of interest were plotted. It was observed that not all pools within a given mining site were marked in the available data. To facilitate our classification task, it became necessary to create two distinct datasets: one comprising cropped imagery with pools (“pools” dataset) and another with cropped imagery excluding pools (“no pools” dataset). To obtain the latter dataset, the coordinates of the marked pools were utilized to ensure that the cropped imagery would not include any pools or mining sites. In the event that not all pools were marked, this could potentially lead to false positives in our classification.

However, we discovered that while it may have appeared that not all pools were marked in the available data, a significant number of pools were nonetheless marked at each mining site. As such, we concluded that in most cases, a segment of the cropped imagery would be able to accurately detect whether a mining site was present, even if the individual pools were not marked. Consequently, we determined that the cropping of the imagery was unlikely to produce major issues in our resulting no-pools dataset. Although there was a small amount of misclassified data, models were designed to be robust enough to identify and account for such flawed data points.

2.3.2 Coordinate Shifting

On visual inspection, it became apparent that certain markers were systematically shifted from the actual coordinates of the pools, as seen in Figure 5. Given the importance of these markers to our analyses, further investigation was necessary. It was discovered that all of the affected

Figure 5: Four images showing the issues with the coordinates of the pools. The top left, bottom left and bottom right images show the systematically miscalibrated coordinates. The top right shows the coordinates correctly placed.

markers originated from a single tile among the five under scrutiny, likely resulting from the use of a different coordinate reference system during the labelling process. While the initial course of action was to discard the entire tile, this proved to be a less-than-ideal solution, resulting in a significant 30% reduction in the available data. A more nuanced approach was eventually adopted, which involved identifying the specific segments of data affected by the displacement (such as locations 0 to 23 in the CSV file) and removing them from the dataset. Ultimately, this method resulted in the removal of 295 pools from consideration, with a corresponding 15% decrease in available data for analysis.

At the outset of the experimentation, these flawed data points in the Skysat satellite imagery were not seen. Consequently, some of our initial analysis was performed on cropped imagery that included these flawed data points. Despite the presence of these flawed data points, we have retained the

results in our report and subsequently compared them with the results obtained from cleaned data.

3 Mine Detection

This section tackles the first objective of this study, namely the identification of illicit rare earth mines (rather than individual pools) using satellite imagery. Three approaches to this task are explored.

Section 3.1 utilises public access Sentinel-2 data from March and November 2022 to calculate and explore a range of spectral indices, exploiting the high spectral resolution of this sensor. Three normalized difference indices designed to highlight moisture, water, and vegetation were used, in addition to an iron oxide index. Masks were generated by heuristically setting and tuning thresholds in these indices. Combination of these masks enabled the identification of regions of interest by calculating the centroids of clusters generated from the complete mask. These regions of interest correspond closely to the mines identified by Global Witness, as evidenced by a **Recall of 0.94** for ROIs within 100m of labeled mines.

Although simple manual thresholding of spectral indices produced good results in identifying general areas of mining activity, Section 3.2 uses a random forest-based semantic segmentation model to find the optimal thresholds in these indices. Using low-shot learning via manual labeling of a small number of landcover classes, the random forest algorithm is able to produce an **F1 score of 0.82** for the task of mine identification using entirely open access, medium resolution satellite imagery.

Finally, Section 3.3 uses a convolutional neural network to conduct binary classification of image crops into "mine" and "non-mine" classes. A Resnet 18 model trained on the ImageNet dataset was fine-tuned using 2000 image tiles of varying sizes cropped from the high resolution SkySat satellite imagery. Though experimentation with various band combinations and image tile sizes, a maximal **F1 score of 0.977** was achieved using 256 x 256 pixel image crops and the standard Red, Green, and Blue band combination.

Together these three approaches demonstrate considerable accuracy for the task of mine identification using satellite imagery, using both medium resolution open-access satellite imagery, as well as high resolution imagery.

3.1 Spectral Indices

3.1.1 Overview

Spectral indices can be calculated from different combinations of two or more spectral bands in a multispectral satellite image. Popular spectral indices include normalised difference vegetation index (NDVI), and normalised difference water index (NDWI) which are designed to highlight pixels belonging to either “vegetation” or “water”. A range of spectral indices, designed to highlight various natural phenomena in addition to water and vegetation, such as rock subjected to oxidation of iron sulphides, and soil have also been proposed. As such, a range of spectral indices were explored, these were calculated as shown in Table 2.

3.1.2 Data

The data used in this analysis was Sentinel-2 public access data as described in Table 1. L2A data from March (timestamp: 20220313T081346) and November (timestamp: 20221118T040039) 2022 were considered.

3.1.3 Approach

Inspecting the plots shown in Figures 6(a)-6(d), it is clear that the NDWI plots give some indication of where the pools are but this is not always consistent. Given that pools vary in both colour and overall quantity of liquid present, considerable variability is to be expected here. NDMI (Normalized Difference Moisture Index) highlights the general locations of the pools more accurately, but also highlights areas of bare rock. NDVI shows a decrease in vegetation in the vicinity of the mines, as well as the roads. The iron-oxide measure clearly outlines roads and pool locations, and is consistent across large areas. MSAVI, SRRE, VARI, and GNDVI were calculated, but are not shown. Both VARI and GNDVI both give very little information, while MSAVI and SRRE produce similar plots to NDVI. As such, the four indices shown in Figure 6 were further explored.

To determine whether it is possible to obtain general regions of interest that may contain a mine, the indices shown in Figure 6 can be used to create masks. Appropriate thresholds for obtaining these masks were

Index	Formula
Normalised Difference Moisture Index	$NDMI = \frac{(X_{nir} - X_{swir})}{(X_{nir} + X_{swir})}$
Normalised Difference Water Index	$NDWI = \frac{(X_{green} - X_{nir})}{(X_{green} + X_{nir})}$
Normalised Difference Vegetation Index	$NDVI = \frac{(X_{nir} - X_{red})}{(X_{nir} + X_{red})}$
Iron Oxide	$IO = \frac{(X_{red})}{(X_{blue})}$
Green Normalised Difference Vegetation Index	$GNDVI = \frac{(X_{nir} - X_{green})}{(X_{nir} + X_{green})}$
Red-edge Simple Ratio	$SRRE = \frac{(X_{nir})}{(X_{rededge})}$
Modified Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index	$MSAVI = \frac{1}{2} \times 2(X_{NIR} + 1) - \sqrt{(2X_{NIR} + 1)^2 - 8(X_{NIR} - X_{Red})}$

Table 2: Spectral indices investigated and corresponding formulae

derived heuristically and are shown in Table 3, note that NDMI can only be calculated with Sentinel-2 data, while the other indices can be calculated using both PlanetScope and SkySat data. To obtain the masks all values above the threshold are set to 1, and all values below the threshold are set to 0.

Index	Sentinel-2 Threshold
Iron-Oxide	1.35
NDVI	0.1
NDMI	-0.1
NDWI	-0.1

Table 3: Thresholds used for different spectral indices.

Note: these thresholds were computed for the Sentinel-2 data, on a single specific image, and then tuned marginally across multiple timesteps. These thresholds vary considerably for different sensors, and in addition, other sensors - particularly those of higher spatial resolution than the 20m Sentinel-2 data, are able to provide different information (for example, NDWI is much clearer in satellite imagery of higher spatial

Figure 6: Output of different indices obtained from Sentinel-2 data.

resolution).

Morphological transformations were applied to the NDVI mask produced in Figure 7 to produce the plots in Figure 8. The opening morphological transformation (erosion, followed by dilation of an image) was applied using OpenCV, with a kernel size of 2x2.

The final mask for a given region is computed by adding the Iron-Oxide, NDMI, and NDWI masks together, followed by the subtraction of the

Figure 7: Masks obtained from spectral indices

morphologically-transformed NDVI mask (see Figure 9(a)). This produces a mask of values in range -1 to 3, for which a further threshold was then set at 2 (i.e. all values 2 or above were set to 1, with everything below equal to zero), as shown in Figure 9(b)). The masks can then be used as such in the pipeline of many different image processing techniques.

Hierarchical Clustering to Obtain Geographical Regions of Interest

Figure 8: NDVI mask obtained after completing morphological transformations on original mask, shown in Figure 6(b).

Figure 9: (a) Final mask, incorporating information from iron-oxide index, NDMI, NDWI and NDVI, and (b) with threshold set to 2, to highlight regions of interest.

Alternatively, the masks can also be used to determine likely mine sites, or regions of interest themselves. To achieve this a hierarchical clustering method: Agglomerative Clustering [8] was employed to cluster the mask

into regions. As the overall number of clusters (or regions of interest) for a given region may vary, this is not specified, but instead a distance threshold of 3 (equivalent to 60m) with linkage set to ward, was applied. The centroid of each cluster can then be calculated with respect to geographical location, providing coordinates of likely mine sites (shown in situ in Figure 10).

Figure 10: Regions of interest as generated by calculating the centroids of clusters generated from complete mask (as shown in Figure 9(b)).

Mask Variability across Time

To assess consistency of masks, the above analysis was carried out on satellite imagery of the same region, taken at different times. Once the geographical coordinates of regions of interest were obtained these were compared across two timesteps (as shown in Figure 11). The distance between each point, and the closest point at an alternative timestep was calculated, and all points with greater than 100m distance were

removed.

Figure 11: Variability of masks across time, at (a) March 2022, and (b) November 2022

The remaining regions of interest are therefore those that appear within approximately the same region across two timesteps - although this could be extended for greater confidence to three or four. Anomalous regions of interest could then be identified by measuring anomalous regions across multiple timesteps. For example, a new region of interest that appears in timestep 2, but disappears in timesteps 3 and 4 is likely to be an anomaly, whereas if it were to remain in approximately the same location in both timesteps 3 and 4, might represent a newly-formed area of mining activity. Within the bounding box specified earlier in the report, comparing March 2022 (2522 regions of interest) to November 2022 (2009 regions of interest) leaves 1610 potential regions of interest. The effect this has on overall accuracy is shown in Table 4.

3.1.4 Results

Within the bounding box defined by: [431350.0, 437330.0, 2819710.0, 2843690.0] (using coordinate projection EPSG: 32647), 701 labelled pools are present. To ascertain the accuracy of the masks in determining regions of interest, the number of pools that fall within a specified distance of the centre of the region of interest was calculated for a range of different distances (see Table 4). The distances were chosen based on

the spatial resolution of Sentinel-2, thus the greatest distance (100) indicates that the AOI encompasses an area of 5 pixel radius.

Recall (single)	Recall (multiple)	Distance from centre of AOI (m)
0.73	0.72	40
0.89	0.87	60
0.95	0.92	80
0.96	0.94	100

Table 4: Accuracy of masks in locating general regions of interest that contain pools and mines. The first column shows recall for regions of interest detected in March 2022, while the second column shows recall for regions of interest detected in March 2022 that are also present in November 2022 (i.e. detected across single, and multiple images, respectively). Recall is used because this approach aims to identify general regions of interest without overlooking mining areas, making false negatives a greater concern than false positives.

3.1.5 Conclusion

Masking Sentinel-2 imagery is a viable approach to determining regions of interest within satellite imagery for detecting mines. Using this to isolate regions of interest, that could then be analysed in further depth (for example, using the approaches later described in this report). The masking procedure is very fast, and is capable of assessing large areas of space quickly, thus it is likely to be most appropriate as a precursor step to applying alternative methods.

Notable limitations of this approach to masking include the sensitivity of the thresholds. An alternative way to approach this would be to attempt to cluster regions of data from the spectral image itself (rather than the generated mask). In particular, certain geographical features - particularly the river - are consistently erroneously classified as regions of interest. One potential way of addressing this could be to isolate larger bodies of water using NDMI with a high threshold, and masking these specific regions, before using NDMI throughout the rest of the area at a lower threshold (to enable mine/pool detection).

3.2 Pixel-based Classification with Random Forests

3.2.1 Overview

Pixel-based image classification, also known as semantic segmentation, is often used for extracting low level features, where the image at hand is classified according to the spectral information [9]. This random forest model aims to perform semantic segmentation to detect mines in the mountainous regions of Myanmar, taking advantage of the high spectral resolution offered by the Sentinel-2 data. The workflow was adapted from [10].

3.2.2 Data

As mentioned in the overview, Sentinel-2 data was used for this model, in particular data from March 2022. In order to have comparable metrics to other approaches, the Area of Interest (AOI) polygon was drawn to be of the same dimensions and coordinates as the SkySat tile named ssc17u_0002. When loading the Sentinel-2 data, a few spectral bands (B1, B9, B10) were excluded, since they were collected at a much lower resolution than the other bands. Images that have high cloud cover were filtered, and the cloudy pixel percentage was thresholded at 10 percent. Building on section 3.1, a mask was applied to the data to isolate the mines using NDVI and NDWI indices in order to assist the classification process. This masking process was applied to the AOI to isolate regions with mines. Three classes were identified to be used in the labelling of data: Mines, Roads and Vegetation. The masking process was very effective in filtering out vegetation and subsequent noise, however, drastic thresholding of NDVI also caused the filtering out of mines obscured by greenery. As such, the NDVI threshold was set at 0.15, and the vegetation class was added for any greenery that might escape the masking process. NDWI was thresholded between -0.2 and 0.2. This mask highlighted the mines quite well, as can be seen in Figure 12.

3.2.3 Model

A random forest model consisting of 500 trees was chosen to classify the chosen pixels according to their spectral profiles. The essential idea

(a) Sentinel-2 imagery of a mine area.

(b) NDWI thresholding.

Figure 12: NDWI thresholds (-0.2, 0.2) applied to a mine area in Sentinel-2 data. They both depict the same area; 12b shows the thresholding results.

behind the random forest model is to average many noisy but approximately unbiased models, decision trees, and hence reducing the variance. This model aims to separate the data into the given classes using thresholds in the chosen input properties. Random Forests are widely implemented in semantic segmentation tasks due to their robustness, computational efficiency in both training and classification and ability to handle multiclass problems [11, 12].

3.2.4 Training

In order to create labels for classes, Polygon objects were created for each class, ensuring that these Polygon objects were created homogeneously across the AOI. Although Sentinel-2 offered superior spectral resolution compared to the SkySat data, the spatial resolution was quite poor. Since the polygon objects had to be created manually, the satellite images from CNES in the Google Earth Engine basemap were used to generate polygons. It should be noted here that the CNES imagery was never fed into the model, it was merely used to simplify the drawing process and increase precision. The reason CNES data was not used was due to the ambiguity in the time frame of when the CNES imagery was obtained: The information on the exact time and date of when this imagery was taken was not available. Thus it was not be

Figure 13: Polygons sampling the three classes: Mines (purple), Roads (orange) and Vegetation (green).

possible to compare the results obtained from the CNES data to the pool locations provided from Global Witness. The CNES imagery was layered behind Sentinel-2 and polygon objects were created using the CNES imagery as a guide to simplify the process, making sure to always cross-reference with the Sentinel-2 data. Then, points were randomly sampled from within the polygons for each class, as using all of the pixels from the polygons would have likely led to overfitting and an imbalance of number of points in each class due to the polygons not being equal in size. Figure 15 shows some of the polygons drawn for each class. Figure 15a and Figure 15b display the polygons drawn over CNES and Sentinel-2 imagery respectively, to contextualize the difference in spatial resolution.

A feature collection was created containing all the sampled points from the two classes, and then randomly divided into a 70-30 split to generate training and validation data. The Sentinel-2 imagery was sampled using these points, such that each point in the feature collection contained the spectral information from Sentinel-2 as well as class labels.

The random forest classification results were visually compared to the image data. The Polygon object set was refined based on these

comparisons, i.e. labelling the falsely classified mines as the correct class or labelling mines that were missed. Then the classification was run again. This was an iterative process, and the Polygon object set was refined until desired results were reached.

3.2.5 Results

The classification was performed on the whole bounding box defined by [431350.0, 437330.0, 2819710.0, 2843690.0] (using coordinate projection EPSG: 32647), and then two smaller test sections were randomly chosen from within the bounding box area. The classification results are visualised for a small section of the AOI on top of CNES imagery in Figure 14. The red areas represent where the model predicted a mine would be; these homogeneous red areas are then converted to blue points for better visualisation. Table 5 shows the confusion matrix and accuracy results for the entire AOI. The overall accuracy over the AOI was computed to be 98 percent, however this estimate should not be taken at face value. There are a number of reasons for the inflated accuracy score, for example spatial auto-correlation in the training data [4].

	Mine	Road	Vegetation	Accuracy
Mine	840	6	0	0.98
Road	12	367	1	
Vegetation	0	1	57	

Table 5: Confusion matrix and accuracy results for the entire AOI

In order to get a better sense of the true performance metrics of the model, the classification predictions were compared to the true pool locations given by Global Witness. It is important to note that the random forest was aiming to predict potential mines, not precise pool locations. Since it was more relevant to measure how many of these pools the predicted mines captured, a buffer of 0.0004 units was added to all of the prediction points produced by the random forest. Figure 14 shows the prediction points plotted alongside true pool locations, with and without buffer. Table 6 shows the performance metrics computed for the two test sections taken from the AOI, alongside their pixel dimensions.

Figure 14: Predictions made by the model, layered over CNES imagery.

Pixel Dimensions	Recall	Precision	F1
1383 x 613	0.83	0.80	0.81
601 x 456	0.76	0.90	0.82

Table 6: Recall, Precision and F1 score calculated for two random test sections taken from the AOI

The performance metrics for both test areas were quite similar. It is important to note that the pool locations provided by Global Witness may not have encapsulated all of the pools in the area, as also mentioned in Section 2.3, which could have led to an increased amount of false positives.

3.2.6 Conclusion

A random forest model was implemented for the pixel-based segmentation task. Overall, good results were achieved across the three performance metrics. However, these results merit further discussion to improve the model performance.

A closer examination of the land cover classes revealed that unfilled mines possessed very similar spectral profiles to roads. This was a difficult issue to solve with semantic segmentation, as classification was solely based on spectral profiles. As both unfilled and filled mines were sampled in training

Figure 15: Before and after a buffer size of 0.0004 units was added to the prediction points, in red. The pool locations given by Global Witness is plotted in blue.

and validation sets, many roads were falsely classified as mines, and some unfilled mines were falsely classified as roads. Thus, this model would be better suited to detecting filled mines. An avenue for further research would be to detect the filling of mines over time by plotting a timeseries of NDWI at one location, as shown in Figure 4. A jump in the NDWI value in a mine area could point to unfilled mines becoming filled.

Finally, further work on optimising the buffer size and spectral index thresholds would be fruitful. It is important to note that the performance of this model largely depends on the efficiency of the masking process, the optimisation of which is necessary for improved performance. It would also be beneficial to use a dataset that offers both high spectral resolution and spatial resolution, which would be helpful in simplifying the generation of training and validation sets.

3.3 Deep learning for mine detection

Having achieved good accuracy in detecting mines via semantic segmentation and open-access inputs, our next aim was to leverage deep learning to classify images into two categories: those containing a mine and those that do not. Deep learning, and in particular convolutional neural networks (CNN), have revolutionised computer vision and tasks such as image classification [13]. The basic building blocks of CNNs are convolutional layers which apply a set of filters to an input image to

extract features. By using multiple filters, CNNs can extract various features, from edges and corners to more complicated features such as faces or cars. While training a CNN from scratch can be time and compute-intensive, transfer-learning has been shown to be an efficient technique to efficiently fine-tune pre-trained models on new dataset [14]. In contrast to training a model from scratch, transfer-learning requires substantially less compute, as most of the model parameters are frozen and only the last layer is trained to predict the dataset at hand. Moreover, transfer-learning based on more generic pre-trained models has been shown to outperform remote sensing-specific models trained from scratch [15]. To classify whether an image contained a mine or not, we therefore used a transfer-learning approach based on a pre-trained CNN.

3.3.1 Data

Coordinates of Pools

For the identification and localization of pools in the region of interest, a dataset of coordinates containing pool locations provided by Global Witness. Consisting of 2792 pools, all at various mining sites, each point had a corresponding x and y coordinate in the 'EPSG:4326' system.

Skysat Pansharpened Imagery

For the imagery data, the Skysat data was utilized. The pansharpened multispectral images were used with four distinct bands: red, green, blue and near-infrared (NIR). The imagery data was taken in the region (421312.5, 2822761.5, 447400.5, 2859726.5) from 07/03/2022 to 12/03/2022.

Data Augmentation

The coordinates of the target pools were taken from the location dataset. These locations were then converted from x and y coordinates to a combined geometrical location in the same coordinate system as the Skysat imagery data (epsg32647). Some pool locations were also removed due to data inconsistencies leading to a final dataset of 2497 pool locations.

The imagery data was taken from the Skysat satellite data, cropped to make a dataset for the analysis. Crops of 1000 pools at random locations

Figure 16: Flowchart showing the data augmentation steps used in the classification task

in the satellite data, for a set size, were extracted for the “Pools” dataset. Crops of 1000 images without any pools were also taken for the “No Pools” dataset. The workflow for the cropping is described in Diagram 16.

Skysat also has an additional channel of near-infrared spectral data on top of the visible red green and blue bands. This data was systematically swapped with the various visible light data for experimentation.

The PyTorch torch.transforms module was used to transform the data before loading it into the model. The training data used several pre-processing transformations which have been shown to make CNN predictions more robust [16]. Specifically, the images were randomly flipped horizontally, their colour altered slightly (colour jittering), rotated, and passed through an affine transformation before being converted into

Figure 17: Flowchart showing the data augmentation steps used in the classification task

a PyTorch tensor. Figure 17 shows the workflow of these transformations and Table 7 gives a more detailed description of the transformations used.

Table 7: PyTorch transformations

Transformation	Additional Arguments
RandomHorizontalFlip	
ColorJitter	brightness=0.4, contrast=0.4, saturation=0.4, hue=0.1
RandomRotation	degrees=20
RandomAffine	degrees=0, translate=(0.2, 0.2)
ToTensor	

3.3.2 Model

As a base model for fine-tuning, we used a pre-trained ResNet18 model from the torchvision.model library. ResNet [17], short for Residual

Network, is a deep neural network architecture which has shown remarkable performance in a wide range of computer vision tasks, including image classification. The key innovation of ResNet compared to other convolutional neural networks is the introduction of residual connections, which allow the network to effectively learn from deeper layers without suffering too much from the vanishing gradient problem. ResNet18 has been trained on the ImageNet dataset, which contains over 1 million labelled images across 1000 different categories. We chose the smallest pre-trained ResNet model in the PyTorch library as the mines and pools in our images tend to have simple geometric features and it is therefore unlikely that even larger models than ResNet18 would substantially improve performance.

3.3.3 Training

Before fine-tuning, we replaced the last fully connected layer of the model with a new layer that outputs to classes - “pool” and “no-pool”. We then froze all the layers of the pre-trained ResNet18 model except for the last layer and trained the model on our labelled dataset of mine and no-mine images using transfer learning. We used a stochastic gradient descent (SGD) algorithm with a learning rate of 0.001 and a momentum of 0.9. We trained the model for 10 epochs with a batch size of 16 and used the cross-entropy loss as the objective function. During training, we monitored the loss and accuracy on the training and validation sets to ensure the model was not overfitting (see Figure 18 for train and test loss of the best performing model based on 256*256 RGB images).

3.3.4 Evaluation

To evaluate the performance of our fine-tuned ResNet18 model, we used a test set of 200 images from one tile to be comparable to other approaches in the team. We computed four metrics– F1 score, accuracy, precision, and recall– to assess the effectiveness of the model. The F1 score is the harmonic mean of precision and recall and is useful for imbalanced datasets. While we constructed our dataset to be 50/50 mine/no-mine images, future application of the model might include very imbalanced datasets. The accuracy measures the proportion of correctly classified images, the precision measures the proportion of true positive

Figure 18: Training and test loss for the best-performing classification model based on 256*256 RGB images.

predictions out of all positive predictions and the recall measures the proportion of true positive predictions out of all actual positive samples. We computed these metrics using the model predicted labels of the test set, which we compared to the ground truth labels.

3.3.5 Results

For classifying images into mine / no-mine categories, we first focused on RGB images of different sizes. Our model performed better on all four metrics for larger images (Table 8). With a resolution of 0.5m per pixel, the 256*256 images covered 128 square meters and performed 4.2% better than 64*64 images in terms of accuracy and 0.043 points better in the F1 score. Notably, the two larger image sizes (128 and 256 square pixels) performed nearly equally well, though the larger images performed slightly better again in terms of accuracy (+0.8%) and F1 score (+0.007). Training loss curves shown in Figure 19 also show the 256*256 crops performed best.

Next, we explored how well the model classified images with 128*128

Table 8: Performance metrics for different image sizes

Image Size	F1	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
64*64	0.934	93.55%	0.959	0.910
128*128	0.970	96.95%	0.969	0.970
256*256	0.977	97.75%	0.981	0.974

Figure 19: Training loss for crops of size 64*64, 128*128 and 256*256.

pixels and three colorbands, one of which was near-infrared (NIR). The best performance in F1 score and accuracy was achieved by training on NIRGB images (Table 9, Figure 20), though all metrics on images including NIR were slightly worse than for models classifying RGB images.

Table 9: Performance metrics for images of size 128*128 and different color channel combinations

Colour Channels	F1	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
R NIR B	0.907	91.10%	0.947	0.871
R G NIR	0.926	92.70%	0.938	0.915
NIR G B	0.939	94.05%	0.959	0.920

Figure 20: Training loss for crops of varying multispectral bands.

Lastly, to be able to directly compare the model performance among different approaches taken in this study, we tested the classification accuracy on 128*128 RGB images for a specific tile. Here, the model had a slightly worse performance compared to previous test datasets with 91.50% accuracy and an F1 score of 0.908 (Table 10).

Table 10: Performance metrics for the evaluation dataset

Dataset	F1	Accuracy	Precision	Recall
Eval	0.908	91.50%	0.995	0.834

3.3.6 Conclusion

Our results contain two main findings. First, models trained on larger images showed a better performance. A reason for this could be that mines don't exist in isolation, but are surrounded by networks of roads, which the model is picking up so that larger images provide more information. However, our model performed well across all tested RGB image sizes and metrics, with only small differences between the smallest and largest image sizes.

Second, models trained on RGB images showed a better classification performance than models trained on images containing NIR bands. This was unexpected, as a visual inspection of the NIR images showed stronger differentiation between mines and their surroundings than RGB images. In retrospect, the reason could be that the pre-trained ResNet model was trained only on RGB images, so our model had to learn the NIR information from scratch. Nevertheless, all NIR image models still achieved good performance across metrics.

4 Pool Detection

Having addressed the first objective of identifying mines, this section addresses the second objective of identifying individual pools within the mines. Two approaches are explored.

Section 4.1 conducts template matching using Normalized Cross-Correlation. Using a reference image, a convolution is run across the larger image to identify regions that are similar to the template. This approach manages to identify pools of a similar shape and color, and Principal Component Analysis applied to the matches even allows for the distinction of filled and empty pools, thereby forming the basis for further research on mine-level activity measures. The approach struggles with generalisation, and is limited by its ability to identify pools of irregular shapes and colours. Nevertheless, template matching effectively constitutes a one-shot learning approach that can be deployed with very few compute resources and a single known mine location to rapidly identify similar structures across a very large area.

Section 4.2 employs a more advanced approach to the identification of precipitation pools through the application of object detection. Similar to the deep learning approach in the previous section, a Faster-RCNN model was fine-tuned using the locations of labelled pools. The model generates bounding boxes around predicted pool locations and assigns them a confidence score. Visual inspection of predictions demonstrates a considerable degree of accuracy in identifying pools; The computation of accuracy statistics is hampered by issues related to coordinate drift (which biases Intersection over Union scores) and unlabelled pools (incorrectly inflating the number of “false positives”). Paradoxically, this acts as a testament to model accuracy given that the Faster-RCNN model identifies a significant number of rare earth precipitation pools that were missed by human labelling.

4.1 Template Matching

4.1.1 Overview

In this first approach at pool detection we explore a technique from image processing, template matching, that finds parts of a image are similar to

a given template image [18]. Template matching has a rich history and is widely used for image processing and a variety of classification tasks [19]. The current state-of-the-art is to use deep learning approaches like Convolution Neural Networks, as we do in Section 4.2, as they are more robust to noise and transformations of the template [19, 20]. However, template matching is a simple and computationally efficient approach, that requires no training, and due to the seeming regularity of the mines it was thought to be a viable approach for detecting them.

4.1.2 Normalised Cross Correlation

Template matching constructs an appropriately defined similarity metric and template image (or kernel) and applies a convolution of the target image. The output of this is a matrix of similarity values that can be used to find area where the image is similar to the kernel. In this case, we will be finding an example pool as the template image and then convolving this across the whole satellite image to find similar sub-images.

Let \mathbf{S} be an image of size $N \times M$ (i.e the whole satellite image) and \mathbf{H} be an $A \times B$ template image (i.e an example pool). We use the notation $\mathbf{S}(x, y)$ to represent the value of a pixel at (x, y) , and define the pixel $(0, 0)$ to be in the center of the image. The convolution is defined as

$$\mathbf{H} * \mathbf{S}(x, y) = \sum_{a=-A/2}^{A/2} \sum_{b=-B/2}^{B/2} \lambda(\mathbf{H}(a, b), \mathbf{S}(x - a, y - b)) \quad (1)$$

where λ is the normalised cross correlation coefficient [21]. Due to the linear nature of this operator, this will work effectively at matching patterns that are similar size and orientations to the template. To this end we simplify the task and focus on only matching circle pools.

4.1.3 Matching Circle Pools

We now provide a short overview of how to apply template matching to detect circle mining pools. As discussed above, template matching begins by choosing an appropriate template. In this work, due to time limitations, we choose a single pool, illustrated in Fig. 22. This pool was chosen because of its clear visibility and regular shape. To make the

pools more distinctive we operated in false color, not RGB. False color replaces the blue band with near infra red which is effective at discerning between vegetation and water from land. To further make the mines more distinctive we increased the contrast through a logarithmic adjustment.

Figure 21: The left panel shows the template image, in RGB, that was used to match the pools. The right panel shows the same image but in false color (RGNi) and with an increased contrast. False color helps differentiate pools from roads, as water and vegetation are clearly pronounced, and the increased contrast makes it easier to detect boundaries.

We show the effect of this in Fig. 22, at two spatial scales, we plot a false color image and its corresponding increased contrast one. It is clear that this is effective at segmenting roads from vegetation (trees) and in making the edges of the pools clearer.

Figure 22: Examples of false color and increased contrast, in the left and right columns respectively, at two different spatial scales. False color clearly differentiates between vegetation (in red) and roads (white). Pools vary from blue to green and black.

The template image is then convolved across the target image, using Eqn. 1, to compute correlations of all sub-images with the template image. This is a matrix of the same size as the target image. We then threshold this matrix, using a value of 0.7. The resulting binary matrix has ones where pools are likely, and zeros where they are not. To find instances of single

pools we group all close values together through clustering.

Figure 23: A visualisation of the template matching pipeline.

This process is depicted in Fig 23; The left most panel displays the area of interest. The center panel shows the result after thresholding the result of template matching. This is a binary image (consisting of only ones and zeros) where a one represents a point that is highly correlated to the input image. The final panel shows the result after clustering these high correlation areas into pools.

4.1.4 Results

Running the template matching algorithm across the area of interest identifies a large number of both filled and empty pools. The left panel of Figure 24 displays the result of running Principal Component Analysis on a subset of the matched pools using the red, green, blue and near infrared channels.

Figure 24: Principal Component Analysis of matches

Two groupings are clearly visible in the data; one following a roughly logarithmic distribution beginning from the origin, with the other group spanning the full range of X values but only negative Y values.

We plot two example pools from the two clusters identified in Figure 24. The two clusters correspond to empty pools (left panel) and filled pools (right panel). Interestingly, some square mines (both filled and empty) are identified via this method despite the original template being a filled circular pool.

Figure 25: Examples of filled and empty pools identified via PCA

We now turn to testing and assessing the performance of template matching as a viable solution to pool detection. Though matching appears to identify several different types of pool, performance is validated on filled, circular mines, which were identified via PCA (See Fig. 24 and Fig 25). We consider two areas of interest: the area defined in the SkySat tile '20220307_070454_ssc6_u0002' (Tile 1) and additionally that in '20220312_042400_ssc17_u0002' (Tile 2).

(a) Predicted pool locations on SkySat Tile '20220307_070454_ssc6_u0002'.

(b) Predicted pool locations on SkySat Tile '20220312_042400_ssc17_u0002'.

Figure 26: Predictions of of mines across two SkySat tiles.

The results of the matching procedure are shown in Figure 26. Each orange point corresponds to a single pool. It is possible to see some false positives (on the left most region of a) which appear to be snow/clouds, however this should be simple to filter out through an ensemble of any of the other approaches.

To validate, we simply compute an intersection of the found circular mines with all of the circular, filled, mines present in each tile. We only report

$$\text{recall} = \frac{\text{number of intersections}}{\text{total number of filled circular mines}}$$

because we do not have a way to asses false positives properly, owing to a number of un-labeled mines present in the skysat imagery (discussed in Section 2.3). We present results in Table 11.

Table 11: Recall scores for the template matching algorithm on filled, circular pools.

	TILE 1	TILE 2
RECALL	0.64	0.44

On Tile 1, this method achieves a surprising score, considering that its simplicity and the use of a single template image. On visual inspection it is not matching every pool but it is finding a large majority of the mining sites. In Tile 2 a worse performance is achieved. On inspection this is because the pools in Tile 2 vary, both in size and composition, making them unlikely to be matched.

4.1.5 Conclusion

Template matching is a simple and computationally efficient way of detecting circle mining pools. It only requires computing the convolution on a region of interest once, and so is useful in the low-resource setting, and only requires a single example template of a pool to be matched. However, as expected, it is limited by the simplicity and linearity of the method, and is only effective at finding similar shaped mines and can suffer from false positives.

There are a number of avenues for further research in the use of template matching for the identification of rare earth mining pools. To improve performance, one could construct many varied templates of mines and then run the model multiple times, in an attempt to match as many ‘types’ of circular mines. It would be interesting to explore the difference in performance across these tiles further to understand why, and if, the mines are more regular in certain parts than others.

To reduce false positives, the masks developed in Section 3.1 could be used to simply discard any pools that are not in likely areas. Since only a single template image is required this could be a useful technique for discovering ‘rare’ pools for which there are only a few training examples and for detecting pools at varying stages, by collecting examples of these stages and running the method independently for each case.

Furthermore, the use of PCA in combination with clustering could be used

in conjunction with other methods such as object detection (explored in the next section) to both accurately identify pools and separate them into filled and empty, offering insights on mine-level activity.

4.2 Deep learning for pool detection

While mine classification based on cropped images worked well using a fine-tuned CNN, the second objective of this study involves the identification of precipitation pools, the characteristic features of mines, on these images. This section conducts another deep learning experiment using a CNN-based object detection model. DL-based object recognition models are usually based on a CNN which generates feature maps highlighting important regions in the image and a second detection network which takes these feature maps as input and produces bounding boxes to identify the location of objects within the image. There has been substantial progress in the field in recent years [22]. Moreover, similar to image classification, a range of pre-trained models are openly available, which is why we decided on using transfer-learning again for the pool detection task.

4.2.1 Data

Object detection requires a labelled dataset with images and corresponding bounding boxes around the objects of interest. Here, we created a dataset with one bounding box per pool for the pool images created for the classification model above. We constructed boxes of size 20x20 pixels, equivalent to 10x10 metres for the high-resolution Skysat satellite dataset. Each box was constructed around each pool, so that the point coordinates of the pool were in the centre of the box. As the pools had different shapes and the points were not always precisely placed on the pools, it was only possible to define a square bounding box of 20x20 pixels as show below in Figure 27. For further work, we propose investigating the model performance for various sizes of bounding boxes.

In total, the dataset consisted of 1000 images of size 128x128 pixels, containing an average of 3.8 pools. Each image contained at least one pool, and over the dataset there were a maximum of twelve pools in a

Figure 27: Example of constructed bounding boxes around labelled pools.

single image. The data was split with 80% for training and 20% for validation.

4.2.2 Model

As a base-model for fine-tuning, we used a Faster R-CNN (Region-based CNN) model [23] with a ResNet-50-FPN backbone from the torchvision library. The model consisted of two main components: a region proposal network (RPN) and a detection network. The RPN generates a set of object proposals which are regions in the image that are likely to contain certain objects. It achieves this by processing feature maps from a backbone CNN and predicting objectness scores and bounding box coordinates. The detection network then takes the feature maps and object proposals from the RPN and generates final object detection by classifying each proposal and refining the bounding box coordinates. The Faster R-CNN model is a widely used object detection framework and is considered to be one of the most accurate object detection models [22], making it an ideal model for pool detection in satellite images.

4.2.3 Training

To fine-tune the model, we used 800 images and ran 10 epochs of stochastic gradient descent optimisation. We set the learning rate to 0.005 and used a momentum of 0.9, as well as a weight decay of 0.0005. The loss curves for training and validation sets are shown in Figure 28.

Figure 28: Loss values reported for training and validation datasets versus number of epochs.

4.2.4 Results

To evaluate the model's performance, we used a separate dataset comprising only one tile to test the model on pools that were not seen during training. However, evaluating the model's performance using standard metrics in object detection tasks was challenging since we only had the approximate positions of the pools, and our bounding boxes did not always perfectly cover the pools. Furthermore, the presence of numerous unlabelled pools made it challenging to use metrics such as precision, which penalise false positives. Nevertheless, visual inspection of the results demonstrates considerable accuracy. Figure 29 shows the

ground truth bounding boxes in green on the left panel, and predicted bounding boxes are shown in red on the right panel.

Figure 29: Ground truth bounding boxes and model predictions on validation set images. Threshold of 0.8 applied to the predicted boxes to aid visualisation.

We observed that false positives occurred in cases where vegetation had outlines matching pool shapes. To address this, we propose a preprocessing step to mask NDVI values above a specific threshold. An alternative approach is to use R-G-NIR instead of RGB data, since it makes it easier to differentiate between pools and non-pools, but this will come with the caveat that fine-tuning models based on RGB data will be harder.

We also observed a small portion of false positives occurring for pools that were only partially in the image, typically at the corner of the image. However, a large portion of false positives were, in fact, not false predictions but true positives that were unlabelled.

Visual inspection of the images revealed that the model performed well in two ways. Firstly, it positioned the predicted bounding boxes closer to the actual pool locations, and secondly, it identified many unlabelled pools with high confidence, as seen in Figure 29 and Figure 30.

Although false positives could arise from vegetation with outlines of

Figure 30: Labeled (green) and predicted (red) bounding boxes with corresponding scores shown.

regular shapes, such as circles or squares, applying a strict NDVI threshold during preprocessing could greatly reduce such false positives. Moreover, the model was generally robust in identifying most true positives, but this can be further improved by fine-tuning the threshold on the model's 'score' (class probability) output per image to keep only bounding boxes with high scores. However, it is worth noting that some true positives may be partially missed if the pools occur between images such that the entire pool is not in either.

Data quality (particularly the presence of coordinate drift and unlabeled pools) precludes the generation of meaningful traditional accuracy statistics used in object detection tasks such as mAP 50 or F1. Instead, model accuracy and data quality issues can both be assessed with greater nuance by plotting the confidence score of predicted mines against the Intersection over Union (IoU) between the predicted bounding box and the ground truth labels. This is shown in Figure 31.

The issues related to the quality of the labelled data are visible in the top left corner of Figure 31. These are predictions with very high confidence—which, based on visual inspection, are almost always true positives—but that overlap very little or not at all with the labeled bounding boxes. This

Figure 31: Labeled (green) and predicted (red) bounding boxes with corresponding scores shown.

reflects coordinate drift (high confidence prediction, low IoU) and unlabelled pools (high confidence prediction, IoU=0)— discussed in greater detail in Section 2.3.

Nevertheless, the regions of highest density in Figure 31 are in the bottom left and top right corners, and are indicative of good model performance. Observations in the top right have a high confidence score, and predicted bounding boxes overlap significantly with the labeled bounding boxes, generating a high IoU value. Conversely, observations in the bottom left corner overlap very little (or not at all) with labeled bounding boxes, but these predicted bounding boxes have very low confidence scores. A confidence score threshold is generally set (heuristically, at 0.8 in the examples in Figures 30 and 29) to filter out low-confidence predictions.

4.2.5 Conclusion

The most immediate next step for this research would be to address issues of data quality. This could be accomplished in a straightforward manner using the predictions from the Faster-RCNN model; unlabelled pools could be identified and labelled by filtering predictions with high confidence and an IoU of 0. Coordinate drift could be solved by substituting drifted bounding boxes with those from predictions that have very high confidence but moderate to low IoU. Finally, a preprocessing step with a strict NDVI threshold would likely remove many false positives, due to predicting vegetation (with some regular shape) as a pool.

Still, our results show that more advanced deep learning methods based on object detection can be applied to high resolution satellite data to detect individual mining pools with a considerable degree of accuracy. The model demonstrates high agreement with the labelled pools, and can even detect unlabelled pools with high confidence.

5 Discussion and Future work

5.1 Discussion

This Data Study Group challenge sought to achieve two main objectives:

1. To automate the identification of illicit rare earth mines in Myanmar using satellite imagery.
2. To train a model to identify individual pools within each mine.

Section 3 tackles the first objective using three approaches; Section 3.1 calculates a range of spectral indices using public access Sentinel-2 data. Simple thresholding of these indices generate regions of interest correspond closely to the mines identified by Global Witness, achieving **Recall of 0.94** for ROIs within 100m of labeled mines. Section 3.2 uses a random forest-based semantic segmentation model to find the optimal thresholds in these indices, and is able to produce an **F1 score of 0.82** for the task of mine identification using entirely open access, medium resolution satellite imagery. Finally, Section 3.3 uses a convolutional neural network to conduct binary classification of image crops into “mine” and “non-mine” classes, achieving a maximal **F1 score of 0.977**.

Section 4 tackles the second objective using two approaches. Section 4.1 conducts template matching using Normalized Cross-Correlation. Though this approach does not generalize particularly well, it is a fast and efficient one-shot learning approach that can be deployed with very few compute resources and a single known mine location to rapidly identify similar structures across a very large area. Section 4.2 employs a Faster-RCNN model to conduct object detection on the precipitation pools. Visual inspection of predictions demonstrates a considerable degree of accuracy in identifying pools, and the Faster-RCNN model even identifies a significant number of rare earth precipitation pools that were missed by human labelling.

Ultimately, this study successfully developed several models to accurately detect both illicit rare earth mines and precipitation pools in Myanmar's Kachin Special Region 1. Nevertheless, there are several avenues for further research. The most immediate would be to tackle issues of data

quality and improve the performance of the models elaborated herein, after which other models and data sources could be explored.

5.2 Future Work

This study relied on two main data sources for training and prediction. SkySat imagery has a high resolution (50cm/pixel), but is expensive and hard to acquire for larger areas or multiple time periods. Sentinel-2 imagery has a much lower spatial resolution (10m/pixel), but is free, available globally, and has a significant historical archive. PlanetScope imagery combines several of the strengths of each data source. It has a high enough resolution (3m/pixel) that individual pools are visible, and is open-access through the NICFI program.

Figure 32: PlanetScope imagery of active precipitation pools

Figure 32 shows PlanetScope imagery of three mines at three different time periods with active precipitation pools. Pools can be seen changing colour from dark blue to white over time.

Beyond using different data sources, further research could apply different models to the data used in this study. Meta AI's Segment Anything Model (SAM)— released shortly after the end of the DSG period— could be applied to the SkySat data to automatically segment not

just the precipitation pools, but all features within a rare earth mine; Figure 33 demonstrates an example of this workflow.

Figure 33: Meta AI's Segment Anything Model (SAM) applied to a rare earth mine

This approach automatically distinguishes the general mining area from the surrounding vegetation, identifies all of the pools, and even segments the buildings. More detailed mine-level metrics could be derived from these segments beyond the count of pools, including the total area of the mine and the number and size of buildings.

Finally, the trained models developed in this study could be applied to the task of identifying rare earth mines in areas beyond the Kachin region of Myanmar. The mine shown in Figure 33 is actually not in Myanmar, but in Jiangxi province, China. Mines in this area were shut down in 2019 due to environmental concerns, immediately preceding the proliferation of this type of mining in Kachin. China's Ministry of Industry and Information Technology estimated the cost of environmental cleanup in Southern Jiangxi could cost around \$5.5 billion, and that the land could take over a century to recover [24]. Automating the detection of these mines– the

task achieved in this study– is a critical step in monitoring the spread of this exceptionally toxic form of mining around the world.

6 Team members

Asli Acar is an MPhys graduate from Durham University. Her research interests lie in particle physics and data science. She directly contributed to this project by performing a pixel-based image segmentation.

Ollie Ballinger (PI) is a Lecturer in Geocomputation at UCL's Centre for Advanced Spatial Analysis. He holds a DPhil from the Oxford Department for International Development. His research mainly involves the application of remote sensing to the study of armed conflict.

Nina Cheongkam Jeong is a PhD candidate in Linguistics at the University of Arizona in the United States. Her research interests lie in Natural Language Processing and Automatic Speech Recognition/Synthesis. She has experience working as a Natural Language Processing Engineer and Speech Specialist for several projects, including the one the U.S. Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency sponsors. She contributed to this project by performing a pixel-based image segmentation.

Ben Gayther is a PhD student in High Energy Physics at University College London (UCL). His research focusses on charged lepton flavour violation as part of the Mu3e experiment, including work on Monte Carlo simulation, calibration and clustering. He was part of the deep-learning team and directly contributed by fine-tuning the Faster R-CNN (pool detection) model.

Ollie Hamelijnc is a PhD student in Computer Science at the University of Warwick and the Alan Turing Institute. His research lies at the intersection between Spatio-temporal Statistics and Machine Learning, with a focus on the computational scalability of multi-task, multi-fidelity models. He contributed directly to the template matching model.

Lucy Mellor is an Innovation Strategy Adviser at DEFRA. She co-facilitated this project.

Gabriella Miles is a final-year Farscope PhD student at the Centre for Machine Vision, Bristol Robotics Laboratory (University of Bristol, and University of the West of England). Her research focuses on the application of machine learning and computer vision methods for the

early diagnosis of neurodegenerative diseases using eye movement. She co-facilitated this project and contributed to it directly in the analysis of spectral indices for Sentinel-2 data.

Joanne Sheppard is a Research Software Engineer at Durham University, who has a wealth of experience in the field of Computer Vision and Image Processing. Her areas of expertise encompass multiple realms, such as biomedical research, security, and facial recognition. She contributed to the development of deep learning techniques for mine detection.

Martin Stoffel is a Research Data Scientist in the Research Engineering Group at the Alan Turing Institute. Previously, he was a Postdoc at the University of Edinburgh working on questions in Quantitative and Evolutionary Genetics in wild animal populations. He contributed with code and ideas to the data processing and model architectures for the deep learning approaches.

References

- [1] Global Witness. *Myanmar's poisoned mountains*. 2022.
URL: https://www.globalwitness.org/en/campaigns/natural-resource-governance/myanmars-poisoned-mountains/?gclid=Cj0KCQiAo-yfBhD_ARIsANr56g4dzQwJIj3Iep-6YEEsVLfHz-mrReBGSGN_ODvb3_qsBY1hgbd518UaAuLHEALw_wcB.
- [2] Adamas Intelligence. *NEW REPORT: Rare Earth Magnet Market Outlook to 2040*. 2023.
URL: <https://www.adamasintel.com/rare-earth-magnet-market-outlook-to-2040/>.
- [3] Leah Burrows. *A clean way to extract rare earth metals*. 2016.
URL: <https://seas.harvard.edu/news/2016/06/clean-way-extract-rare-earth-metals>.
- [4] ESA. *SENTINEL-2 MISSION GUIDE*. Planet. 2023. URL: <https://sentinel.esa.int/web/sentinel/missions/sentinel-2> (visited on 07/14/2023).
- [5] ESA. *Spatial Resolution*. 2023.
URL: <https://sentinels.copernicus.eu/web/sentinel/user-guides/sentinel-2-msi/resolutions/spatial>.

- [6] MIT. *Increasing efficiency and decreasing cost and environmental damage of rare earth refinement*. 2016.
URL: <https://web.mit.edu/12.000/www/m2016/finalwebsite/solutions/greenrefining.html>.
- [7] Planet.
High-Resolution Imagery with Planet Satellite Tasking. Planet. 2023.
URL: <https://www.planet.com/products/hi-res-monitoring/> (visited on 04/13/2023).
- [8] F. Pedregosa et al. “Scikit-learn: Machine Learning in Python”. In: *Journal of Machine Learning Research* 12 (2011), pp. 2825–2830.
- [9] Sibaruddin et al.
“Comparison of pixel-based and object-based image classification techniques in extracting information from UAV imagery data”. In: *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* 169.012098 (2018).
- [10] Ollie Ballinger. *Refinery Identification*. 2023. URL: <https://alan-turing-institute.github.io/DSGFeb2023GW/refineries.html>.
- [11] Jun Xiong et al. “Nominal 30-m Cropland Extent Map of Continental Africa by Integrating Pixel-Based and Object-Based Algorithms Using Sentinel-2 and Landsat-8 Data on Google Earth Engine”. In: *Remote Sensing* 9 (Oct. 2017), p. 1065.
DOI: [10.3390/rs9101065](https://doi.org/10.3390/rs9101065).
- [12] Pelletier et al.
“Assessing the robustness of Random Forests to map land cover with high resolution satellite image time series over large areas”. In: *Remote Sens. Environ.* 187 (2016), 156–168.
DOI: [10.3390/rs9101065](https://doi.org/10.3390/rs9101065).
- [13] Waseem Rawat and Zenghui Wang. “Deep convolutional neural networks for image classification: A comprehensive review”. In: *Neural computation* 29.9 (2017), pp. 2352–2449.
- [14] Hoo-Chang Shin et al.
“Deep convolutional neural networks for computer-aided detection: CNN architectures, dataset characteristics and transfer learning”. In: *IEEE transactions on medical imaging* 35.5 (2016), pp. 1285–1298.
- [15] Rafael Pires de Lima and Kurt Marfurt.
“Convolutional neural network for remote-sensing scene

- classification: Transfer learning analysis”.
In: *Remote Sensing* 12.1 (2019), p. 86.
- [16] Adrian Spurr et al. “Self-Supervised 3D Hand Pose Estimation From Monocular RGB via Contrastive Learning”.
In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*. 2021, pp. 11230–11239.
- [17] Kaiming He et al. “Deep residual learning for image recognition”.
In: *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. 2016, pp. 770–778.
- [18] Nazanin Sadat Hashemi et al.
Template Matching Advances and Applications in Image Analysis. 2016. DOI: [10.48550/ARXIV.1610.07231](https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.1610.07231).
URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1610.07231>.
- [19] P. R. S. Swaroop and Neelam Sharma. “An Overview of Various Template Matching Methodologies in Image Processing”.
In: *International Journal of Computer Applications* 153 (2016), pp. 8–14.
- [20] Ian J. Goodfellow, Yoshua Bengio, and Aaron Courville.
Deep Learning. <http://www.deeplearningbook.org>.
Cambridge, MA, USA: MIT Press, 2016.
- [21] J.P. Lewis. “Fast Normalized Cross-Correlation”.
In: *Ind. Light Magic* 10 (Oct. 2001).
- [22] Anamika Dhillon and Gyanendra K Verma.
“Convolutional neural network: a review of models, methodologies and applications to object detection”.
In: *Progress in Artificial Intelligence* 9.2 (2020), pp. 85–112.
- [23] Shaoqing Ren et al. “Faster R-CNN: Towards Real-Time Object Detection with Region Proposal Networks”.
In: *CoRR* abs/1506.01497 (2015). arXiv: [1506.01497](https://arxiv.org/abs/1506.01497).
URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1506.01497>.
- [24] Michael Standaert. *China Wrestles with the Toxic Aftermath of Rare Earth Mining*. Yale E360. 2019. URL: <https://e360.yale.edu/features/china-wrestles-with-the-toxic-aftermath-of-rare-earth-mining> (visited on 04/13/2023).

**The
Alan Turing
Institute**

**turing.ac.uk
@turinginst**